

STUDIES IN SESQUITERPENES. PART II. SYNTHESES OF METHYLCADALENES

BY SUKH DEV

5-Methyl-, 8-methyl- and 3-methyl-cadalenes have been synthesised.

In connection with our investigations on the sesquiterpenes of the cadinene group it became necessary to ascertain the properties of all the five possible methylcadalenes, and 1-methyl-6-ethyl-4-*isopropyl*-, and 1-ethyl-6-methyl-4-*isopropyl*naphthalene. Of the five methylcadalenes, 2-methyl- and 7-methyl-cadalene have been prepared previously by Campbell and Soffer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 417), the syntheses of the remaining three are reported in this paper.

The necessity for the preparation of these compounds arose in connection with the location of the double bonds of a new bicyclic sesquiterpene (cadinene group). The method is similar to that employed by Ruzicka and Sternbach (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1940, 23, 124) for the location of the nuclear double bond of *dextro* pimaric acid. The method has also been used by Campbell and Soffer (*loc. cit.*) in revising the structure of cadinene. A mono-oxide, prepared by the action of one mole of perbenzoic acid (or percamphoric or perphthalic acid) on one mole of the sesquiterpene (here, the word sesquiterpene will refer to a sesquiterpene of the cadinene group), will react with methyl magnesium iodide, introducing a methyl group in the molecule :

Thus, the position of the additional methyl group in the molecule will reveal the position of the ethylenic linkage.

The method can be extended to include the ketones and the primary and secondary alcohols of this group. The position of a keto group in the molecule can be readily established by identifying the methylcadalene produced by the dehydrogenation of the tertiary carbinol obtained by the reaction of magnesium methyl iodide on the ketone. The method has been used by Bradfield and co-workers in fixing the position of the carbonyl group of tetrahydro-eremophilone, a sesquiterpene ketone of the eudalene group (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 667). The secondary alcohols can be oxidised to the corresponding ketones by the elegant method of Oppenauer (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1937, 56, 137) and then the method used. Similarly, the aldehyde obtainable by the oxidation of a primary alcohol can be employed.

The application of these methods will be reported in future communications.

1 : 5 : 6-Trimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (IV).—2 : 5-Dimethyl-8-isopropyltetralone-1 (I), prepared from *p*-cymene (Sukh Dev and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 25, 13), is treated with magnesium methyl iodide to give a mixture of the carbinol (II) and its dehydration product. The mixture is completely dehydrated with 90% formic acid giving 1 : 5 : 6-trimethyl-4-isopropyl-7 : 8-dihydronaphthalene (III). Dehydrogenation of this hydrocarbon by means of selenium gives the required 5-methylcadalene (IV).

1 : 3 : 6-Trimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (XII).—Toluene is condensed with methylsuccinic anhydride in nitrobenzene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to give β -(*p*-toluyl)- α -methylpropionic acid (V). This reaction has been previously reported by Mayer and Stamm (*Ber.*, 1923, 56, 1424). They carried out the reaction in excess of toluene as a solvent for 2 hours at room temperature and 2 hours on the water-bath and obtained a 77% yield of the crude product, which consisted of a mixture of β -(*p*-toluyl)- α -methylpropionic acid (39.6%) and β -(*p*-toluyl)- β -methylpropionic acid (56.6%). However, by our procedure, β -(*p*-toluyl)- α -methylpropionic acid is the chief product and is obtained in an excellent yield of 80-86%. The melting point of our compound is 174-75°, whereas Mayer and Stamm have reported it as 169-71°. In view of this difference it became necessary to confirm the structure of our product. This has been done by synthesising this acid from 4-acetyl-toluene (XIII). This is brominated with one mole of bromine to give the ω -bromo compound (XIV). The latter is condensed with the sodium salt of

methylethylmalonate, giving the *is*osuccinic ester (XV), which is hydrolysed and decarboxylated to (V), m.p. 173-74° (mixed m. p. with the Friedel-Craft's product, 173.5-174.5'). This synthesis has also been reported by Mayer and Stamm (*loc. cit.*).

Next, the inverse Grignard's reaction of magnesium methyl iodide on methyl β -(*p*-toluyl)- α -methylpropionate (VI) was carried out. By following the details of a procedure recommended by Kloetzel for a similar reaction (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1708) we could only get yields of 50-60%. There are many variables in this reaction which can affect the yield. A systematic investigation reveals that the amount of the Grignard reagent, the time and the temperature at which the hydrolysis of the reaction complex is carried out, are the most important factors. By proper control of these variables, consistent yields of 90-95% of the crude material could be easily obtained. For one mole of the ester 1.7 moles of the Grignard reagent should be employed. The decomposition of the reaction complex should be carried out by adding dilute hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) to the reaction mixture, cooled to about 2°-5°, and then the whole thing should be worked up immediately after the complex is dissolved. If the reaction mixture is allowed to remain in contact with the mineral acid for a longer period, a considerable amount of the unsaturated acid produced is lost through lactonisation, the separation of which from any unreacted keto-ester is very difficult. The γ -(*p*-tolyl)- γ : α -dimethylvinylacetic acid (VII) is obtained as a viscous liquid, which does not crystallise.

The crude acid could not be purified by distillation, since in all cases the acid completely lactonised on distillation at 2 to 3 mm.

The catalytic reduction of (VII) with Adam's platinum oxide catalyst was not attempted, since the acid could not be easily purified. Reduction with Raney-nickel in alcohol at 80° and 70 lbs. pressure could not be achieved. Hence the compound was submitted to reduction with hydriodic acid and red phosphorus. The reduced acid could only be obtained in 50% yield, while a considerable amount of the material is found in a neutral fraction. If the time of reaction be increased, the yield of the reduced acid falls and that of the neutral fraction rises. In one instance (40 hours' refluxing) the

distillation under reduced pressure. The acid is reduced with hydriodic acid and red phosphorus to yield 7-(2-*m*-xylyl)-valeric acid (XX). In this case also, a small neutral fraction is obtained, which contains the corresponding tetralone. This acid has been previously prepared by Heilbron and Wilkinson from 2 : 4-dimethylacetophenone (involving 8 steps) (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2538).

But the present method is much simpler (4 steps) and the yields are very good. The acid is cyclised by anhydrous aluminium chloride to give 4 : 5 : 7-trimethyltetralone-1 (XXI). The ketone is treated with magnesium *iso*-propyl bromide when an unstable carbinol (XXII) is obtained, the latter is dehydrated with 90% formic acid and then dehydrogenated with sulphur to yield 8-methylcadalene (XXIII).

All the methylcadalenes, thus synthesised, have been characterised by the preparation of suitable derivatives. By far the best reagent for the characterisation of these hydrocarbons appears to be trinitrobenzene. Its molecular compounds are very stable, sparingly soluble in alcohol, and can be easily obtained pure by a single crystallisation from 80% acetic acid. The reagent is recommended for the characterisation of all the methyl-naphthalenes.

The melting points of the derivatives of all the five methylcadalenes are tabulated below :

Methylcadalene.	Picrate. m.p.	Styphnate. m.p.	T. N. B. compound. m.p.	T. N. T. compound. m.p.
2-Methyl-*	143-44°	170-71°	168-69°	—
3-Methyl-	162-63°	—	165°	—
5-Methyl-	102.5-103.6°	130-31°	160-61°	87-8°
7-Methyl-*	122-23°	—	—	—
8-Methyl-	108-8.5°	—	118-18.5°	—

* Campbell and Soffer, *loc. cit.*

Work on the syntheses of 1-methyl-6-ethyl-4-*isopropyl*- and 1-ethyl-6-methyl-4-*isopropyl*-naphthalene is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

1 : 5 : 6-*Trimethyl*-4-*isopropyl*naphthalene (IV)

1 : 5 : 6-*Trimethyl*-4-*isopropyl*-7 : 8-*dihydronaphthalene* (III).—A solution of 2 : 5-dimethyl-8-*isopropyl*tetralone-1 (I, prepared from *p*-cymene according to the method of Sukh Dev and Guha, *loc. cit.*) (10.0 g., 1 mol.) in dry ether (40 c.c.) was added gradually from a dropping funnel with continuous swirling to a well cooled (ice and salt) solution of magnesium methyl iodide (Mg, 1.6 g., 1.25 mol.; MeI, 10 g., 1.5 mol. and anhydrous ether, 50 c.c.). The mixture was left in the ice-bath for 15 minutes and then allowed to attain the room temperature (32°). The reaction went on quite vigorously at room temperature for half an hour, when a white solid separated. The reaction was completed by refluxing for 5 hours and the product decomposed by adding on to ice and ammonium chloride. The ether layer was separated, washed with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removing the ether, a slightly reddish yellow viscous oil consisting chiefly of the carbinol was left. This was completely dehydrated by warming it with 90% formic acid (20 c.c.) on the water-bath for 2½ hours. 1 : 5 : 6-*Trimethyl*-4-*isopropyl*-7 : 8-*dihydronaphthalene* was isolated in the usual manner and purified by distillation over sodium as a colourless, mobile liquid, b.p. 140-43°/2.5 mm., yield 9.0 g. (90%).

1 : 5 : 6-*Trimethyl-4-isopropylnaphthalene* (IV).—The above dihydromethylcadalene (9.0 g.) and selenium (4.5 g.) were heated together for 1 hour at 280° and then at 300°-310° for 24 hours and finally at 320° for 4 hours and then the product was worked up in the usual manner. The hydrocarbon (IV) was purified by several distillations over sodium as a colourless, mobile liquid, b.p. 132°/1.5 mm., yield 5.0 g. (56%). (Found : C, 90.12 ; H, 9.56. $C_{16}H_{20}$ requires C, 90.56 ; H, 9.43 per cent).

The *picrate*, prepared in the usual manner, was recrystallised thrice from alcohol as deep red needles, m.p. 102.5-103.5°.

The *stypnate*, prepared from styphnic acid (0.5 g.) and the hydrocarbon (0.5 g.) in 5 c. c. of alcohol was recrystallised thrice. The pure compound separated from alcohol in orange needles, m. p. 130-31°.

Trinitrobenzene Compound.—Trinitrobenzene (0.5 g.) was dissolved in hot alcohol (20 c.c.) and the methylcadalene (0.5 g.) added. The mixture was heated till a clear solution was obtained, and then allowed to crystallise slowly. The crystals were filtered, washed with a small amount of cold 80% acetic acid and then with alcohol and dried. The product was recrystallised from 80% acetic acid (10 c.c.) as long, golden yellow needles, m.p. 160-61°. Further crystallisations did not raise the m.p.

Trinitrotoluene Compound.—T.N.T. (0.5 g.) was dissolved in hot 80% acetic acid (5 c.c.) and the hydrocarbon (0.5 g.) was added and the mixture heated till a clear solution was obtained ; it was allowed to cool slowly. The compound was removed by filtration and recrystallised twice from 80% acetic acid (3 to 5 c.c.) as deep yellow needles, m.p. 87-88°. The compound could not be crystallised easily from alcohol due to its dissociation in the solvent.

1 : 3 : 6-*Trimethyl-4-isopropylnaphthalene* (XII)

β -(*p*-ToluyI)- α -methylpropionic Acid (V) : *Condensation of Methylsuccinic Anhydride with Toluene*.—Pyrotartaric anhydride (34.2 g., 1 mol.) was condensed with toluene (30.6 g., 1.1 mol.) in dry nitrobenzene (150 c.c.) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (89.1 g., 2.1 mols.). The details as given for the preparation of β -(*p*-cymoyl)- α -methylpropionic acid (Sukh Dev and Guha, *loc. cit.*) were followed. Yield of the crude product (m.p. 160-62°) was quantitative. The product was crystallised from 90% acetic acid as colourless plates, m.p. 174°-75°, yield 53.0 g. (85.7%).

Synthesis of (V) from 4-Acetyltoluene.—4-Acetyltoluene (6.7 g., 1 mol.) in dry ether (10 c.c.) was brominated with bromine (8.0 g., 1 mol.) following the details given for the preparation of ω -bromoacetophenone ("Organic Synthesis", Vol. XIX, p. 24), yield 8.5 g. (80%), m.p. 49°-50° (cf. Kunckell, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 577, 1713).

4-Methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone (8.0 g., 1 mol.) was condensed with the sodium salt of methyldiethylmalonate (from sodium, 0.9 g. and ester, 6.5 g.)

in dry benzene (30. c.c.). The condensation was effected, and the *is*osuccinic ester hydrolysed and decarboxylated by following the details given for the preparation of β -(*p*-cymoyl)- α -methylpropionic acid (Sukh Dev and Guha, *loc. cit.*). The product crystallised from acetic acid (90%) in colourless plates, m.p. 173-74°, yield 4.0 g. (52%) (mixed m.p. with the Friedel-Craft's condensation product, 173.5-174.5°).

Methyl β -(p-ToluyI)- α -methylpropionate (VI).—Acid (45.0 g.), methanol (100 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (conc., 6.0 c.c.) were refluxed for 10 hours and worked up in the usual manner. The crude product was recrystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless, lustrous, long plates, m.p. 46°, yield 90-93%. (Found : C, 70.95 ; H, 7.54. $C_{13}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 70.90 ; H, 7.27 per cent).

γ -(*p*-Tolyl)- γ : α -dimethylvinylacetic Acid (VII).—A Grignard solution of magnesium methyl iodide was prepared from magnesium (2.2 g., 1.7 mol.), MeI (15.0 g.) and dry ether. (25 c.c.). The ester (11.0 g., 1 mol.) was dissolved in dry ether (70 c.c.) and chilled in an ice-salt bath (-15°) to below 0° and the Grignard solution was added in a very thin stream with continuous swirling (20-30 mins.) Each drop reacted vigorously with the precipitation of a white solid. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand in the ice-bath with occasional swirling till it attained the room temperature (25°, 2 hours) and it was then refluxed on the water-bath for 3 hours ; it was finally allowed to stand overnight (12 hours). The white solid had by that time completely changed into a viscous semi-solid. The product was cooled in an ice-bath to about 5° and dilute HCl (1 : 1, 60 c.c.) was introduced in a thin stream from a dropping funnel with vigorous shaking (10 mins.). The complex should have decomposed by then, if not, the mixture should be thoroughly shaken to dissolve the complex. The reddish ether layer was then separated, washed once with water and extracted four times with dilute Na_2CO_3 solution. The extract was treated with norit and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid (Congo red) and the liberated oil extracted with ether (thrice). The ethereal solution was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and the solvent removed, when a slightly viscous reddish yellow oil was left, yield 9 to 9.5 g. (90-95%). The product was unsaturated to bromine in chloroform and was used as such in the next step.

γ -(*p*-Tolyl)- γ : α -dimethylbutyric Acid (VIII).—The above crude acid (18.0 g.) was reduced by refluxing for 16 hours with hydriodic acid (*d* 1.7, 100 g.) and red phosphorus (12.0 g.) at 130-140°. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether several times. The ethereal extract was washed with water twice and extracted with dilute sodium carbonate solution (4 times). The ether solution which contained the neutral products was kept apart for being treated later. The alkaline extract was clarified with norit and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid (Congo red). The acid was extracted with ether (thrice) and the extract was washed with a sodium bisulphite solution to remove any iodine and then it was washed

with water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The ether was distilled off and the crude acid left behind was purified by distillation as a colourless, viscous liquid, b. p. $176^{\circ}/7.5$ mm., yield 9.0 g. (50%). (Found : C, 75.99 ; H, 9.09. $C_{13}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 75.72 ; H, 8.73 per cent) (cf Ruzicka and Ehmman, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, 15, 154).

The ethereal solution containing the neutral products was first washed with sodium bisulphite solution to remove the free iodine and it was then washed once with water, and dried. The ether was removed and the residue was twice fractionated carefully from a modified Claisen's flask. Two main fractions were obtained.

Fraction.	B.p.	Yield.	Remarks.
A	$110-14^{\circ}/4$ mm.	2.0 g.	Colourless, mobile liquid
B	$135-40^{\circ}/4$	4.0	Do

Fraction A.—It was once distilled over sodium. The hydrocarbon (1.5 g.) was dehydrogenated with sulphur (0.65 g.) at 230° for 30 minutes and then at 260° for 20 minutes. 1 : 3 : 6-*Trimethylnaphthalene* was isolated in the usual manner and purified by distillation over sodium as a colourless, mobile liquid, b.p. $115^{\circ}-20^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 75%.

The *picrate* was obtained as deep orange needles (alc.), m.p. $114^{\circ}-15^{\circ}$ (Lit.* m.p. 115°). The *styphnate*, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from alcohol in yellow, silky needles, m.p. 126° (Lit.* m.p. 126° . Ruzicka has given a m.p. of 148° at page 155, while in a table on page 142, he gives 126° as the melting point).

Fraction B.—This was identified to be 2 : 4 : 7-*trimethyltetralone-1* (IX) by preparing the 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, as a bright red, crystalline powder (benzene & petrol), m.p. $220.5-22^{\circ}5'$ (mixed m.p. with an authentic sample remained undepressed).

2 : 4 : 7-*Trimethyltetralone-1* (IX).— γ -(*p*-Tolyl)- γ : α -dimethylbutyric acid (15.0 g.) in dry benzene (30 c.c.) was converted into the acid chloride by phosphorus pentachloride (16.8 g. covered with 30 c.c. of dry benzene) in the usual manner and the acid chloride without being isolated was cyclised by anhydrous aluminium chloride (10.6 g.). The details as given for the cyclisation of γ -(*p*-cymyl-2)- α -methylbutyric acid (Sukh Dev and Guha, *loc. cit.*) were followed. The reaction was complete in 20 to 30 minutes. The product was obtained as a colourless, mobile liquid, b.p. $131^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 80-88%. (Found : C, 82.88 ; H, 8.69. $C_{13}H_{18}O$ requires C, 82.97 ; H, 8.51 per cent).

The 2 : 4-*dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from benzene-petrol mixture as a bright red crystalline powder, m.p. $220.5-22^{\circ}5'$.

1 : 3 : 6-*Trimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene* (XII).—A Grignard solution of magnesium isopropyl bromide was prepared from magnesium (3.1 g., 1.6 mol.),

* Ruzicka & Ehmman, *loc. cit.*

isopropyl bromide (15.6 g., 1.6 mol.) and ether (75 c.c.). The Grignard solution was chilled in an ice-salt bath and the above ketone (15.0g., 1 mol.) in dry ether (75 c.c.) was added in a thin stream with swirling (10 mins.). The reaction mixture became brownish with the separation of a viscous heavy liquid. The mixture was kept as such for 15 minutes and it was then allowed to reach the room temperature (25°) during $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The reaction was completed by refluxing for 3 $\frac{1}{2}$ hours and then leaving overnight (13 hours). The product was decomposed with ice and ammonium chloride and worked up in the usual manner. The crude carbinol was dehydrated by heating with 20 c.c. of acetic anhydride for 3 hours on a steam-bath and the reaction mixture was fractionated from a modified Claisen's flask. The required unsaturated hydrocarbon distilled as a colourless, mobile liquid, b.p. 135-40°/3.5 mm., yield 13.0 g. (76%).

The dihydromethylcadalene (13 g.) was dehydrogenated with selenium (7 g.) (see under 5-methylcadalene) to give 3-methylcadalene, which was purified by repeated distillations over sodium, as a colourless, mobile liquid, b.p. 145°/4 mm., yield 60%. (Found : C, 91.17 ; H, 9.40. C₁₆H₂₀ requires C, 90.56 ; H, 9.43 per cent).

The *picrate*, prepared in the usual manner, was recrystallised thrice from alcohol as silky, orange needles, m.p. 162-63°. The *trinitrobenzene compound* was prepared by the method described under 5-methylcadalene and recrystallised from 80% acetic acid in silken yellow needles, m.p. 165°.

1 : 6 : 8-Trimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (XXIII)

β -(2-m-Xyloyl)-propionic Acid (XVII) - Succinic anhydride (35.0 g., 1 mol.) was condensed with *m*-xylene (40.8 g., 1.1 mol.) in a dry nitrobenzene (150 c.c.) solution in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (104. g., 2.2 mols.). [For details, see under β -(*p*-toluyl)- α -methylpropionic acid]. Yield of the crude product (m.p. 107°-9°) was quantitative. The product was recrystallised from 5 parts of a mixture of benzene (3 parts) and ligroin (b.p. 80-90°, 4 parts) in colourless, long, fine needles, crystallising in stars, m.p. 111-12°, yield 62-65 g. (86-90%) (Barnet and Sanders, *loc. cit.*, m.p. 108°, 111°-12°, 114°).

Methyl β -(2-m-Xyloyl)-propionate (XVIII).—The above acid (60.0 g.), methanol (120 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (8.0 c.c.) were refluxed for 7 hours and the product worked up in the usual manner. The ester was purified by distillation, b.p. 151-52°/2.5 mm., yield, 56.0 g. (87.5%).

γ -(2-m-Xylyl)- γ -methylvinylacetic Acid (XIX).—The reaction was carried out in exactly the same way as given under γ -(*p*-tolyl)- γ : α -dimethylvinylacetic acid, yield 70-80%.

γ -(2-m-Xylyl)-valeric Acid (XX).—The crude acid (12.0 g.), hydriodic acid (*d* 1.7, 60.0 g.) and red phosphorus (8.0 g.) were refluxed at 130-140° for 30 hours. The duct was worked up in the usual manner. The reduced

acid was purified by distillation in *vacuo* as a colourless, viscous liquid, b. p. 170°-173°/3 mm., yield 60%. (Found : C, 76.68 ; H, 8.75. $C_{13}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 75.72 ; H, 8.73 per cent).

4 : 5 : 7-Trimethyltetralone-1 (XXI).—The above acid was cyclised by using the method employed for the ring-closure of γ -(*p*-cymyl-2)- α -methylbutyric acid (Sukh Dev and Guha, *loc. cit.*). In this case it became necessary to reflux the reaction mixture for 15 minutes in order to dissolve all the aluminium chloride. The product was obtained as a colourless liquid, b. p. 155-59°/9 mm., yield 77%. (Found : C, 83.00 ; H, 8.72. $C_{13}H_{16}O$ requires C, 82.97 ; H, 8.51 per cent).

The 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was prepared by the sulphuric acid method and recrystallised from benzene (containing a small amount of petrol, b. p. 86-90°) in deep red plates, m. p. 231-32°.

1 : 6 : 8-Trimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (XXIII).—*iso*Propyl magnesium bromide was reacted with the above ketone (10.0 g) in the same way as described under 1 : 3 : 6-trimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene.

The crude carbinol (11.0 g.), which was obtained as a reddish viscous syrup, was dehydrated with 90% formic acid (20 c. c.) in the usual manner. The crude unsaturated hydrocarbon was purified by distillation in vacuum as a colourless, mobile liquid, b. p. 130°-35°/3 mm., yield 6.0 g. (53% overall yield) ; quite a good amount of the substance was retained as a resinous residue in the distillation flask.

The hydrocarbon (6.0 g.) was dehydrogenated with sulphur (1.0 g.) first at 230° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and finally at 260° for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The methylcadalene was worked up in the usual manner and purified by distillation over sodium in vacuum as a colourless, mobile liquid, b. p. 144-47°/3 mm., yield 3.6 g. (Found : C, 90.34 ; H, 9.81. $C_{16}H_{20}$ requires C, 90.56 ; H, 9.43 per cent).

The *picrate* was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol till the m. p. became constant ; dark red needles, m. p. 108°-108.5°.

The *trinitrobenzene compound* was twice recrystallised from 80% acetic acid in orange needles, m. p. 118°-18.5°.

The author's thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Guha. for the kind interest he has taken in this work.